

Complexes of Ditertiary Phosphine and Arsine Oxides with Metal Ions Part III. Complexes of Tin(IV) and Titanium(IV) Halides with Oxides of *o*-Carbomethoxyphenyltertiaryarsines

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Complexes of tin (IV) chloride, bromide and titanium (IV) chloride have been prepared with ligands. *o*-Carbomethoxyphenyldiphenyl-arsine oxide (CMPDPAO) and *o*-carbomethoxyphenyldi (*p*-tolyl) arsine oxide (CMPDTAO), in which stoichiometry of ligand to Lewis acid is one to one. On the basis of infrared data, all the tin (IV) complexes in solid state have been assigned a hexacoordinated structure involving coordination through a carbonyl and arsenyl oxygen atoms, while in nitrobenzene an equilibrium between ionic and covalent structures has been proposed. On the other hand titanium (IV) complexes have been assigned a hexacoordinated structure involving coordination through ethereal oxygen of ester group and arsenyl oxygen.

COMPLEXES of tin(IV) and titanium(IV) halides with a variety of ligands containing nitrogen, phosphorus, arsenic or oxygen as donor atoms have been studied¹⁻⁸. Wilkins and Haendler⁹ have reported complexes of pyridine-N-oxide with tin(IV) fluoride, while Sheldon and Tyree¹⁰ have reported one to one complexes of tin(IV) chloride and bromide with triphenylarsine oxide. Frazer and co-workers¹¹ have reported complexes of triphenylphosphine oxide with tin(IV) halides. Sandhu and Sandhu¹² have reported one to one adducts of tin(IV) halides with oxides of 1,2-ethylenebis(diphenylphosphine/arsine (EDPO/EDAO) and 1,4-butylenebis(diphenylphosphine/arsine (BDPO/BDAO) Lappert¹³ has reported complexes of ethyl acetate with tin(IV) and titanium (IV) halides.

Thus complexes of tin(IV) and titanium(IV) halides with ligands containing either tertiary arsine oxide or ester group have been reported but there is no mention of complexes of tin(IV) and titanium(IV) halides with ligands containing both tertiary arsine oxide and ester group together. Keeping this in view, complexes of tin(IV) chloride, bromide and titanium(IV) chloride with ligands: *o*-carbomethoxyphenyldiphenylarsine oxide (CMPDPAO) and *o*-carbomethoxyphenyldi (*p*-tolyl) arsine oxide (CMPDTAO) have been prepared. Stoichiometry of these complexes has been established with the help of elemental analysis and their properties such as molar conductance and infrared spectra have also been studied. Complexes of CMPDPAO and CMPDTAO with mercury(II) halides have already been reported¹⁴.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of ligands :

Ligands CMPDPAO and CMPDTAO were prepared by the method reported earlier¹⁴.

Purification of tin(IV) and titanium(IV) halides :

Tin(IV) chloride, bromide and titanium(IV) chloride were purified by the methods reported in literature^{4,12}.

Preparation of complexes :

Titanium(IV) complexes were isolated by the addition of dry petroleum ether (60°-80°) to the benzene solutions of ligand and titanium(IV) chloride.

Tin(IV) complexes were formed, when benzene solutions of ligand and tin(IV) halide were allowed to stand for a few minutes.

All the manipulations were carried out under dry conditions. The complexes were finally dried under vacuum.

Analysis :

Tin and titanium were estimated as SnO₂ and TiO₂ respectively. Halogen was determined by Volhard's method.

Infrared Spectra :

Infrared spectra of ligands was recorded in Perkin, Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer 337 in the range 4000 to 666 cm⁻¹.

Molar conductance :

Molar conductance in nitrobenzene was measured in Toshnival Conductivity Bridge type CLOI/OI.

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Results and Discussion

Analytical results of all the complexes of tin(IV) and titanium(IV) correspond to one to one stoichiometry (Table 1). Molar conductance data is also given in Table 1. Infrared spectral data of the ligands and complexes are listed in Table 2.

of 24 cm⁻¹ (in both cases) in ν(C-O) stretching frequency as compared to the respective ligands. This suggests that coordination is taking place through ethereal oxygen of the ester group of the ligand^{15,16}. Also the ν(As = O) group frequency undergoes a fall of 35-40 cm⁻¹ on complexation, suggesting coordination through arsenyl oxygen. Thus the ligands

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF TIN (IV) AND TITANIUM (IV) COMPLEXES

Complex	M.P. °C	Molar conductance (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	Analysis			
			Required		Found	
			Metal	Halogen	Metal	Halogen
SnCl ₄ .CMPDPAO	125	8.7	18.52	22.16	18.27	21.89
SnBr ₄ .CMPDPAO	120	14.8	14.50	39.07	14.82	39.68
SnCl ₄ .CMPDTAO	116	14.6	17.75	21.23	17.46	20.86
SnBr ₄ .CMPDTAO	105	14.8	14.02	37.79	14.42	37.38
TiCl ₄ .CMPDPAO	235	0.2	8.42	24.91	8.16	25.10
TiCl ₄ .CMPDTAO	230	0.3	8.02	23.75	7.84	23.43

TABLE 2. INFRARED SPECTRA OF CMPDPAO AND CMPDTAO AND THEIR COMPLEXES WITH TIN(IV) AND TITANIUM(IV) HALIDES (CM⁻¹)

Ligand/Complex	Carbonyl stretching frequency (C = O) (I)	Carbonyl stretching frequency (C-O) (II)	As = O (III)	Shifts in		
				(I)	(II)	(III)
CMPDPAO	1640	1290	840	—	—	—
SnCl ₄ .CMPDPAO	1600, 1666	1316, 1299	805	-40, +26	+26, +9	-35
SnBr ₄ .CMPDPAO	1575, 1666	1316, 1296	800	-65, +26	+26, +6	-40
TiCl ₄ .CMPDPAO	1694	1266	800	+54	-24	-40
CMPDTAO	1625	1290	835	—	—	—
SnCl ₄ .CMPDTAO	1600, 1681	1316	805	-25, +56	+26	-30
SnBr ₄ .CMPDTAO	1600, 1666	1316	805	-25, +41	+26	-30
TiCl ₄ .CMPDTAO	1694	1266	800	+69	-24	-35

In the complexes of CMPDPAO with tin(IV) chloride, two strong bands at 1666 cm⁻¹ and 1660 cm⁻¹ are observed. A band at 1640 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to ν(C = O) stretching frequency in free CMPDPAO. This suggests a decrease of 40 cm⁻¹ in ν(C = O) stretching frequency on complexation while ν(C-O) stretching frequency increases by 26 cm⁻¹ on complexation, which suggests coordination through carbonyl oxygen of the ester group of the ligand¹⁵. The other band at 1666 cm⁻¹ in the aforementioned complex may be due to spitting in the crystal lattice, since the spectra has been recorded in solid state. The ν(As = O) group frequency is lowered by 35 cm⁻¹ on complex formation suggesting coordination through arsenyl oxygen to the metal ion. Thus the ligand CMPDPAO, behaves as bidentate. Infrared spectral data of other three tin(IV) complexes. SnCl₄.CMPDTAO, SnBr₄.CMPDPAO and SnBr₄.CMPDTAO has been found to be similar to that of SnCl₄.CMPDPAO.

Infrared spectral data of titanium(IV) complexes, TiCl₄.CMPDPAO and TiCl₄.CMPDTAO, indicate upward shifts of 55 cm⁻¹ and 70 cm⁻¹ in carbonyl stretching frequency and corresponding fall of shifts

CMPDPAO and CMPDTAO behave as bidentate in titanium(IV) complexes also.

The complexes of SnCl₄ and SnBr₄ with ditertiary phosphine and arsine oxides have been assigned a hexacoordinated structure¹². In view of this a hexacoordinated structure may also be assigned to these complexes. Their insolubility in common organic solvents and sensitivity to moisture precludes the determination of their molecular weights. However, molar conductance of tin(IV) complexes in nitrobenzene varies from 8.7-14.8 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ which can be attributed to an equilibrium between covalent and ionic structures in nitrobenzene.

Titanium(IV) complexes have been found to be non-electrolytes in nitrobenzene.

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